

POLITENESS AND RESPECT IN THE DIGITAL AGE: THE KEY TO EFFECTIVE DIGITAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

The transfer of politeness principles from reality to the virtual environment took place at the same time as communication moved, or rather developed, to the new realities. And in order for the internet to develop, the same principles that have shaped today's societies have also been found on the new networks. And because the new digital age is characterised by rapid interaction and constant communication in all its forms, respect and politeness remain fundamental to maintaining a pleasant and constructive virtual environment. Adapting politeness principles in the online environment has become a necessity in order to avoid conflicts, misinformation and the development of a toxic virtual space, while at the same time contributing to the creation of a respectful online environment conducive to positive communication. Respect remains perhaps the most important principle for the harmonious development of a relationship, even online, and communication must meet this requirement. This article takes a theoretical look at transferring principles from the real world to the virtual world and stresses the importance of respect and politeness in online communication.

Keywords: politeness, online communication, respect, strategies, online community, online behavior

1. Introduction

The fundamental principle of respect for others remains as important in social media as in traditional communication. Using positive language, and avoiding offensive expressions and aggressive tones are key to maintaining a pleasant virtual environment. In addition, empathy in communication plays a crucial role. Encouraging and supporting others in difficult moments, understanding different perspectives and listening carefully to others' opinions contribute to a respectful and open online space. In the online environment, the principles of politeness and etiquette have been reinterpreted to suit

new ways of communicating and the specificity of social media platforms. From the use of appropriate address forms to respecting the personal space of others, users have had to adapt to the requirements and norms of digital communication. In a world where content can go viral in seconds, the impact of words and actions online has become more evident than ever.

In social media, disagreements and conflicts are inevitable, but how they are handled can make the difference between escalation and resolution. Principles of politeness are essential in managing these situations. Users are encouraged to avoid offensive language, focus on arguments and avoid knee-jerk responses. A calm and respectful approach can turn a debate into a constructive discussion where all participants can express their opinions without damaging relationships or the atmosphere. But most of the time there are disagreements and fights between politeness and impoliteness. (Tsoumou, J., 2023).

Principles of politeness also include responsibility for accurate and transparent information. “misinformation can spread rapidly” (Stănescu, G. C., 2023), users are encouraged to check sources, avoid distributing false information and provide information resources to support their arguments. This not only contributes to a more truthful online environment, but also to respect the principles of trust and accountability. Social media brings together people from different cultural, social and ideological backgrounds. Principles of online civility extend to respecting diversity and different perspectives. Users are encouraged to be open to opposing views, to avoid expressing judgements too quickly and to contribute to constructive debate with sound and well-researched arguments.

As well as adapting traditional principles of politeness, social media has also given rise to new ethical rules on privacy, copyright and personal data protection. Users are encouraged to respect these rules and help promote an ethical online culture by sharing content responsibly and respecting the rights and privacy of others. And these issues of politeness must also be taken into account in the context of the transition to the next phase of Web 3.0, the metaverse. (Vlăduțescu Ș.&Stănescu, G.C., 2023)

2. How politeness principles apply online

In the digital age, principles of civility have become the anchor that holds the online environment to a high level of respect and consideration. Adapting these principles to social media helps build a pleasant and constructive virtual space where positive communication and genuine relationships can thrive. Respect, empathy, managing conflict and promoting diversity become fundamental to creating an online environment where every individual feels valued and listened to. By adhering to these principles, users become pioneers of a healthier and more respectful digital environment.

Communication is going through a period where speed is perhaps the main quality that subjects relate to, especially those of the younger generation (Stănescu, G.C., 2018). Communication is fast, through all kinds of channels and by all kinds of means. The word is no longer at the centre of communication, but neither has it completely disappeared. The emergence of platforms built around images (photos, videos, reels, shorts, visual effects) is a testament to this. Facebook, Instagram, TikTok or Youtube, Snapchat, Telegram, Whatsapp and many others are all made possible by the internet and compete (if not surpass) the classic channels of communication such as radio, television or the classic newspaper. These developments not only bring people together in simple (face-to-face) communication, but also facilitate the transfer of information across business, commerce, services and more, and are therefore increasingly used.

„With little exaggeration, we may call the 21st century the age of networks. Networks are becoming the nervous system of our society, and we can expect this infrastructure to have more influence on our entire social and personal lives than did the construction of roads for the transportation of goods and people in the past. In this sense ‘information highway’ is an appropriate term. The design of such basic infrastructures is crucial for the opportunities and risks to follow”. (Jan van Dijk, 2020)

3. Visual and Multimedia Communication

In the digital age of images, visual and multimedia communication has become a central pillar of online interactions. Social media platforms abound with images, videos, infographics and other

forms of visual content that bring an extra dimension to the expression of ideas, emotions and communication in general. Images have a unique power to convey messages and emotions in an instant. In social media, images such as photos, illustrations, memes and infographics are used to add context and support the written message. These images can make communication more engaging and easier to understand, helping to capture attention and convey information in an effective way. Visual content can also add a personal touch to communication, helping users connect emotionally with the topics being discussed. Personal photos, videos of everyday life and visual stories can help build stronger and more authentic online relationships. In addition, in the company-human relationship, the internet has contributed significantly to the development of a new type of relationship. It is much more direct, focused on the individual, feedback is much quicker and more personal, and the feeling offered translates into the offer materialising and the deal being done. It is the kind of relationship that could only develop so well online, because conventional reality involves too many filters. This new type of communication is preferred by companies that have invested heavily in developing a "language" that can bridge this gap and reach the consumer directly. Multimedia communication brings diversity of expression by combining different elements such as text, image, sound and movement. This gives users the opportunity to express their ideas in a more complex and engaging way. From video vlogs to multimedia presentations, these combined forms of communication allow a greater variety of expression and influence the way messages are perceived. Visual communication and multimedia can be powerful tools to create engaging and memorable content. However, context and audience must be taken into account. Cultivating creative and respectful expression involves both carefully selecting visual content and avoiding misuse or abuse of multimedia elements.

In terms of politeness, visual and multimedia communication plays a crucial role in conveying emotions in a more authentic way. For example, the use of emoji can help express feelings and tone, helping to make the message clear and avoid misinterpretation. However, it is important to exercise caution in the use of visual and multimedia content online. What may be funny or appropriate in one context may

be interpreted differently in another. The use of images or content that may be offensive or infringe copyright should also be avoided.

Visual and multimedia communication adds depth and variety to online communication, allowing users to express their ideas and emotions in creative and engaging ways. However, responsibility in the choice and use of this content remains essential to maintain a polite and respectful virtual environment, where messages are interpreted appropriately and without compromising politeness and sensitivity in communication.

In the online environment, communication has developed in a unique and exciting way, leading to the emergence of a specific language and symbols that transcend linguistic and cultural boundaries. Online communication has influenced the evolution of language and symbols, contributing to understanding and politeness in digital interactions. A new language has emerged, characterised by abbreviations, acronyms and unique terms. Words like "LOL" (Laugh Out Loud), "BRB" (Be Right Back) and "OMG" (Oh My God) were adopted to save time and convey emotions in a concise way. This abbreviated language, known as "leetspeak" or "netspeak", has become an integral part of online communication, and users use it to express quick reactions or emphasise emotions. In addition, the adaptation of words and phrases to reflect the sounds and language spoken online has led to the development of original forms of communication that sometimes deviate from traditional linguistic norms. These subtle changes in language have helped to create a distinct online identity and build a community of users with shared values and norms.

Emoji and stickers have become an integral part of online communication, adding a visual and emotional dimension to messages. These small but expressive symbols can help convey tone and feelings more accurately than the words themselves. From smiles and hearts to complex facial expressions and gestures, these symbols enrich online communication and support polite and empathetic expression. However, using emoji and stickers correctly in a variety of contexts can be complex. The meaning of these symbols can vary depending on culture and personal interpretation. It is therefore important to avoid confusion and ensure that these symbols are used with care and in accordance with the context.

Online communication has also led to the development of a new type of symbol: memes and viral images. These are images or sequences

of images accompanied by short texts that have a humorous message or a subtle cultural reference. Memes have become popular ways of communicating and expressing opinions in a funny and engaging way. However, it is important to bear in mind that the meaning and tone of memes can vary depending on the audience and cultural knowledge. What may be funny to some may be unclear or even offensive to others, so it is essential to use them with care and respect for others.

In recent years, the influence of content formats such as "shorts" and videos from platforms like TikTok and Instagram Reels have grown tremendously and have made their mark on the development of online language and symbols. These short video content formats have become extremely popular and have brought new dimensions to online communication.

A new era of communication was ushered in with the popularisation of short video content formats such as "shorts" and videos in TikTok and Instagram Reels. These formats offer a unique way to communicate through moving images and sounds, bringing an extra dimension to online communication. By using movement, facial expressions and music, these formats aim to convey messages in a more engaging and interactive way.

Shorts and videos in TikTok and Reels not only offer a new way of conveying information, but have also given rise to a visual language of their own. Users develop trends, movements and gestures that become recognisable to their online community. These visual signs become symbols that transcend linguistic boundaries and enable fast and expressive communication.

On platforms like TikTok and Instagram Reels, people from all over the world share their stories and perspectives in an interactive and dynamic way. This leads to greater openness to diversity and inclusion. Messages and videos that promote tolerance, understanding and respect for diversity can go viral and influence online discussions in a positive way.

While short video content formats bring with them innovative opportunities for communication, that must be taken to respect ethical and polite rules. The fact that such content is distributed quickly and can go viral means that its impact can be significant. Respecting copyright, avoiding offensive content and promoting a positive virtual

environment are essential to maintaining respectful and authentic online communication.

In addition to the fun and content-creating aspects of short video formats, they can also exemplify politeness and social norms in a unique way. For example, users can use facial expressions and movements to show empathy, support or respect in their messages. In addition, adapting to current trends can show that users are connected to common culture and values, promoting respectful and authentic communication.

The development of online language and symbols is closely linked to the evolution of digital communication. This new set of tools brings with it an increased responsibility for politeness and respect. Although online language may seem more informal, rules of politeness remain essential for maintaining respectful and sensitive communication in the online environment.

In conclusion, the development of online language and symbols reflects the evolution of communication in the digital age. They not only enrich online interactions, but also create opportunities for deeper expression and understanding of opinion and emotion. However, their correct and respectful use is essential to maintain positive communication and avoid misunderstandings.

The marketing figures accompanying the new platforms seem to be in their favour, as the number of ads and interactions of this kind has also increased considerably. This means a migration of marketing to these areas as well, to the detriment of traditional communication channels. Whereas a few decades ago advertising was only possible on radio/television/newspapers, advertising now accompanies websites, media platforms, and the figures are clear proof that these platforms not only provide entertainment but also make money.

Overall, innovations in short video content have brought a new and exciting dimension to online communication. The "shorts" format and videos in TikTok and Reels have generated new ways of communicating through moving images and sounds. These content formats have contributed to the development of a distinct visual language and the creation of symbols that facilitate understanding and politeness in digital interactions. However, responsibility in their use remains important to maintain respectful and authentic communication

online. In short video content formats, such as "shorts" and videos in TikTok or Reels, words can become secondary to images and sounds. In these formats, visual expression, movement and sound play a dominant role in conveying messages and emotions. However, words and the way they are used can have a significant impact, even if they are used less. Even though images and sounds are the focal points of short video formats, words can be used to enhance understanding, add context or convey complex messages. For example, additional short text can clarify the message of a video or emphasise a particular emotion. At the same time, words can provide a personal and authentic touch, adding value to interaction and communication. The way we choose to formulate words and messages can influence their tone and perception. In the context of short video formats, where vocal expression may be limited or non-existent, written words become even more important. Using words that express empathy, respect and politeness can contribute to respectful and authentic communication, even in the absence of verbal communication.

Written words can also be interpreted in different ways by different people. Thus, word choice and wording must be done carefully to avoid misunderstandings or misinterpretations. In the context of short video formats, words can add an extra dimension of understanding when used in harmony with visual expression. Well-placed and relevant text can enhance the impact of an image or add a touch of humour or drama.

Although images and sounds play a central role in visual communication through short video formats, words should not be ignored. They can enhance understanding, add context and convey complex emotions and information. In addition, the way we use words can influence the tone, perception and impact of messages. In the context of politeness and respect, the choice of words and the way we phrase them remain key to maintaining authentic and respectful online communication.

4. Conclusions

Transferring the principles of respect and politeness from the real world to the virtual world is essential for maintaining a pleasant and constructive virtual environment. Respect, empathy, managing conflict, and promoting diversity become fundamental to creating an online

environment where everyone feels valued and listened to. The responsible use of visuals and multimedia is also essential to maintain a polite and authentic virtual environment where messages are interpreted correctly. Therefore, in today's fast-paced digital environment, adapting the principles of politeness and respect online is crucial to maintaining a positive and constructive virtual environment. Respecting the principles of politeness online is not only a sign of good manners but a way to build genuine relationships, promote positive communication and help create a friendlier and more respectful online space for all users.

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